

Adenosine receptors. Part 1 : (2*S*,3*S*,4*R*,5*R*)-2-(4-(alkyl/arylamino)-5*H*-pyrrolo[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-7-yl)-5-(hydroxymethyl)pyrrolidine-3,4-diol derivatives as possible adenosine receptor agonists[†]

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Abstract : 6-Substitued adenosine derivatives are well known adenosine receptor agonists and a few of these derivatives are being used as therapeutic agents. A series of novel N⁶-substitued-9-deaza adenosine or N⁴-substitued pyrrolo[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine derivatives with aza sugar were prepared through the displacement of chloro derivative with various amines. Corresponding chloro derivative was prepared from hydroxyl compound by the reaction with phosphorus oxychloride under buffer conditions using appropriately protected aza sugar moiety.

Keywords : N⁴-Substitued pyrrolo[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine derivatives, 6-substitued adenosine derivatives with aza sugar, adenosine receptors, adenosine receptor agonists.

Introduction

Extracellular adenosine acts on a family of four cell surface receptors termed as adenosine receptors (ARs). The ARs are four subtypes : A₁, A_{2A}, A_{2B} and A₃^{1,2}. The ARs are G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs) and consist of a single polypeptide chain which transverses the membrane from the extracellular side beginning at the N-terminus to form seven transmembrane helices (TMs). The structure-activity relationship (SAR) of adenosine derivatives as AR agonists has been exhaustively probed. Most of the known AR agonists are derivatives of purine nucleosides, either adenosine or xanthosine³⁻⁵.

The SAR of adenosine ligands as the A₁AR was recently reviewed⁶. In general, substitution of adenosine at the N⁶-position with a wide range of alkyl, cycloalkyl, and arylalkyl groups increases selectivity for the A₁AR. These include N⁶-cyclopentyladenosine (CPA, **1**) and its 2-chloro analogue (CCPA, **2**) and are among the most potent and selective A₁AR in wide use as pharmacological agents⁷. Several A₁-selective adenosine derivatives, including GW493838 (**3**), Selodensoson (**4**), GR79236 (**5**), Tecadenoson (**6**) and CVT-3619 (**7**) are also reported in the literature^{8,9}.

1 : R = H: CPA
2 : R = Cl: 2-Chloro CPA

3 : GW493838

[†]In honour of Professor K. C. Joshi on the occasion of his 88th birthday.

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For A₃AR, substitution with an N⁶-benzyl group or substituted benzyl group increases selectivity and the examples are IB-MECA (**17**), CI-IB-MECA (**18**) and LJ-529 (**19**)²⁰⁻²².

ing acetic anhydride and pyridine in the presence of catalytic amount of DMAP to give compound **22**. This step was necessary to avoid complications in the next step of chlorination. Next, conversion of keto/hydroxyl at 4-position in **22** to chloro compound **23** was very challenging. The direct conversion using POCl₃ resulted into many complications since the acidic nature of POCl₃ would result into deprotection of Boc group of aza sugar. A number of buffer reagents to avoid the acidity of POCl₃ were attempted but use of only triethylamine.HCl and

Based on these findings it was decided to prepare analogs of C-nucleosides which are not reported in the literature. The present paper deals with the synthesis and characterization of some pyrrolo[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine derivatives and also substituting oxygen of ribose with nitrogen (aza sugar). On the basis of knowledge gained on the work done on various adenosine receptor agonists, it was quite challenging to synthesize some new pyrrolo[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine derivatives, having substitutions at position-4.

All synthesized compounds, (2*S*,3*S*,4*R*,5*R*)-2-(4-(alkyl/arylamino)-5*H*-pyrrolo[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-7-yl)-5-(hydroxymethyl)pyrrolidin-3,4-diol derivatives, were fully characterized by ¹H NMR and Mass spectra.

Biological activity of these compounds is under investigation and will be reported later.

Results and discussion

The synthesis of the desired molecules involved a number of steps starting from 7-((2*S*,3*S*,4*R*,5*R*)-3,4-dihydroxy-5-(hydroxyl-5-(hydroxymethyl)pyrrolidin-2-yl)-3*H*-pyrrolo[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-7-yl)-pyrrolidin-4(5*H*)-one hydrochloride (**20**). Because of the reactivity of nitrogen of aza sugar moiety, it was decided to first protect this nitrogen with *tert*-butoxycarbonyl group using Boc anhydride and triethylamine in methanol/water mixture resulting into compound **21**. Aliphatic hydroxyl groups of aza sugar in compound **21** were then protected with acetyl group us-

N,N-dimethylaniline in acetonitrile at 70–75 °C gave satisfactory results in our hands and the important compound **23** was obtained in reasonable yield²³. Then we tried conversion of chloro into various substituted amines which was successful but subsequent hydrolysis of acetyl group and Boc group did not give pure final targets **25a-f**. Therefore we had to deprotect acetyl group first with sodium methoxide in methanol to give compound **24**. The final targets **25a** to **25f** were prepared by refluxing compound **24** with different amines (primary/secondary) in the presence of triethylamine using *n*-butanol as solvent followed by treatment with 2 *N* HCl for deprotection of Boc group.

Experimental

General procedures :

All solvents and chemicals were used as purchased without further purification. The progress of all reactions was monitored on Merck pre-coated silica gel plates (with fluorescence indicator UV254). Column chromatography was performed with silica gel (230–400 mesh size) with the solvent mixtures specified in the corresponding experiments. Spots were visualized by irradiation with ultraviolet light (254 nm). Melting points (m.p.) were taken in open capillaries on a Stuart melting point apparatus using Veego VMP-D and are uncorrected. Proton ¹H NMR spectra recorded on model BRUKER ADVANCE DPX

Scheme 1. Synthesis of compounds 25a-f.

Reagents and conditions : (i) di-*tert*-butyl dicarbonate, triethylamine, methanol, water, RT, 19 h; (ii) pyridine, acetic anhydride, DMAP, RT, 24 h; (iii) POCl₃, triethylamine.HCl, *N,N*-dimethyl aniline, acetonitrile, 70–75 °C, 15 min; (iv) sodium metal, methanol, RT, 1 h; (v) amine, *n*-butanol, triethylamine, 120 °C; 2 *N* HCl.

Table 1. Physico-chemical properties of novel N⁶-substituted 9-deaza adenosine derivatives

Sr. no.	Compd.	Amines used (NR ₁ R ₂)	Molecular formula	Molecular weight	M.p. (°C)
1.	25a		C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₃	319.36	183–186
2.	25b		C ₁₇ H ₂₅ N ₅ O ₃	347.41	167–169
3.	25c		C ₁₆ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₃	333.39	156–158
4.	25d		C ₁₆ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₃	333.39	114–118
5.	25e		C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₃	319.36	219–222
6.	25f		C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₅ O ₃ Cl	389.84	175–178

300 using DMSO-*d*₆ as solvent. Mass spectra recorded on model AGILENT G1946 (1100 Series). The purity of compounds was checked by HPLC on model AGILENT 1260 series at wave length 260 nm and the column used

was LichroCART 125-4 HPLC Cartridge, Purospher RP-18 (5 μm).

Preparation of (2*R*,3*R*,4*S*,5*S*)-(tert-butyl-3,4-dihydroxy-2-(hydroxymethyl)-5-(4-oxo-4,5-dihydro-3*H*-pyrrolo[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-7-yl)pyrrolidine-1-carboxylate (21) :

To a solution of 7-((2*S*,3*S*,4*R*,5*R*)-3,4-dihydroxy-5-(hydroxyl-5-(hydroxymethyl)pyrrolidin-2-yl)-3*H*-pyrrolo[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-7-yl)pyrrolidin-4(5*H*)-one hydrochloride (20, 50.0 g, 165.2 mmol) in water and methanol (1 : 1, 1.0 L) was added triethylamine (50.14 g, 495.6 mmol) at room temperature followed by (Boc)₂O (110.6 g, 506.8 mmol). The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 19 h. The solid obtained was filtered and washed with water (1.0 L) and dried to afford title compound (43.4 g, 71.7%) as an off-white solid.

¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 11.18 (1H, s), 7.86 (1H, s), 7.33 (1H, s), 4.74–4.53 (1H, m), 4.26 (1H, s), 4.03 (1H, s), 3.97 (1H, s), 3.70–3.53 (2H, m), 1.33–1.06 (9H, m); MS (ES⁺) 367.3 (M+1), (ES⁻) 365.3 (M-1).

Preparation of (2*R*,3*R*,4*S*,5*S*)-2-(acetoxymethyl)-1-(tert-butoxycarbonyl)-5-(4-oxo-5*H*-pyrrolo[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-7-yl)pyrrolidine-3,4-diyl diacetate (22) :

To a stirred solution of (2*R*,3*R*,4*S*,5*S*)-(tert-butyl-3,4-dihydroxy-2-(hydroxymethyl)-5-(4-oxo-4,5-dihydro-3*H*-

pyrrolo[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-7-yl)-pyrrolidine-1-carboxylate (**21**, 25.0 g, 68.2 mmol) in pyridine (37.8 g, 477.9 mmol) was added *N,N*-dimethylaminopyridine (167 mg, 1.37 mmol) and acetic anhydride (24.38 g, 238.8 mmol) at room temperature. The reaction mixture was stirred at this temperature for 24 h. TLC was checked to ensure the completion of reaction. The reaction mass was diluted with water (100 mL) and extracted with CHCl₃ (2 × 100 mL). The combined organic layers were washed with water (100 mL), 2 *N* HCl (3 × 50 mL) and brine (50 mL) and dried over sodium sulphate and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated to furnish desire product (26.0 g, 77.38%) as foam.

¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 11.93 (1H, s), 7.98 (1H, s), 7.65 (1H, s), 5.66 (1H, m), 5.33 (1H, m), 5.15 (1H, m), 4.35 (2H, m), 4.19 (1H, m), 2.11–1.93 (9H, m), 1.14 (9H, m); MS (ES⁺) 493.3 (M+1), (ES⁻) 491.3 (M-1).

Preparation of (2R,3R,4S,5S)-2-(acetoxymethyl)-1-(tert-butoxycarbonyl)-5-(4-chloro-5H-pyrrolo[3,2-d]pyrimidin-7-yl)pyrrolidine-3,4-diyl diacetate (23) :

To a stirred solution of (2*R*,3*R*,4*S*,5*S*)-2-(acetoxymethyl)-1-(*tert*-butoxycarbonyl)-5-(4-oxo-4,5-dihydro-3*H*-pyrrolo[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-7-yl)pyrrolidine-3,4-diyl diacetate (**22**, 40.0 g, 81.22 mmol) in acetonitrile (160 mL, 4.0 mL/g of SM) was added triethylamine.HCl (20.8 g, 151.11 mmol) at room temperature. The temperature of the reaction mixture was raised to 55–60 °C and *N,N*-dimethyl aniline (10.8 g, 89.12 mmol) followed by POCl₃ (49.8 g, 324.79 mmol) were added at 55–60 °C [Caution : POCl₃ addition was exothermic]. The reaction mixture was slowly heated to 70–75 °C and stirred at this temperature for 15 min. TLC was checked to ensure the completion of reaction. The reaction mass was cooled to room temperature and diluted with EtOAc (400 mL) and washed with water (400 mL). The aqueous layer was further extracted with EtOAc (250 mL). The combined organic layers were washed with water (200 mL), brine (200 mL) and dried over sodium sulphate. After filtration, the filtrate was concentrated to give crude product (37.5 g) as a reddish oily mass. The crude was purified by flash chromatography over silica gel (230–400 mesh) using 40–80% EtOAc in *n*-hexane to furnish pure compound (22.23 g, 53.57%) as light brown solid.

¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 12.34 (1H, s), 8.25 (1H, s), 7.90 (1H, s), 5.83 (1H, m), 5.43 (1H, m), 5.02 (1H, m), 4.45 (2H, m), 4.05 (1H, m), 2.01–1.86 (9H, m), 1.18 (9H, m); MS (ES⁺) 511.4 (M+1), (ES⁻) 509.3 (M-1).

Synthesis of 2-(4-chloro-5H-pyrrolo[3,2-d]pyrimidin-7-yl)-3,4-dihydroxy-5-hydroxymethylpyrrolidine-1-carboxylic acid tert-butylester (24) :

A solution of (2*R*,3*R*,4*S*,5*S*)-2-(acetoxymethyl)-1-(*tert*-butoxycarbonyl)-5-(4-chloro-5*H*-pyrrolo[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-7-yl)pyrrolidine-3,4-diyl diacetate (**23**, 10.0 g, 19.57 mmol) was dissolved in MeOH (100 mL) and sodium metal (0.5 g, 21.74 mmol) was added and stirred for 1 h at room temperature. The reaction mass was concentrated to dryness to yield crude product as a dark brown semi solid mass. This was purified by flash column chromatography over silica gel (230–400 mesh) using 5–12% MeOH in dichloromethane to afford 2-(4-chloro-5*H*-pyrrolo[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-7-yl)-3,4-dihydroxy-5-hydroxymethylpyrrolidine-1-carboxylic acid *tert*-butylester (7.4 g, 98.27%) as pale yellow solid.

¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 11.84 (1H, s), 8.33 (1H, s), 7.97 (1H, s), 5.75 (1H, m), 5.33 (1H, m), 5.12 (1H, m), 4.54 (2H, m), 4.13 (1H, m), 1.18 (9H, m); MS (ES⁺) 385.3 (M+1), (ES⁻) 383.3 (M-1).

General method for preparation of compounds 25a-f :

A solution of 2-(4-chloro-5*H*-pyrrolo[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-7-yl)-3,4-dihydroxy-5-hydroxymethylpyrrolidine-1-carboxylic acid *tert*-butylester (**24**, 0.25 g, 0.65 mmol), the corresponding primary or secondary amines (3.25 mmol) and triethylamine (1.31 g, 12.95 mmol) was stirred at reflux temperature for 10–15 h. Completion of the reaction was monitored by TLC. The reaction mass was concentrated to dryness and was purified by flash chromatography over silica gel (230–400 mesh) using 5–12% MeOH in dichloromethane to afford 2-(4-(substituted amino)-5*H*-pyrrolo[3,2-*d*]pyrimidin-7-yl)-3,4-dihydroxy-5-hydroxymethylpyrrolidine-1-carboxylic acid *tert*-butylester as light greenish/light brown/light yellow solid. This material was then treated with 2 *N* HCl (26 mmol) and was stirred at RT for 1 h. Completion of the reaction was monitored by TLC. The mixture was concentrated to dryness and purified through preparative TLC eluting with CMA 80 (CHCl₃-80 : MeOH-18 : NH₄OH-2) to furnish

the title compound as free base. Yield varied from 60 to 75%.

(2*S*, 3*S*, 4*R*, 5*R*)-2-(4-(cyclopropylmethylamino)-5*H*-pyrrolo[3, 2-*d*]pyrimidin-7-pyrimidin-7-yl)-5-hydroxymethylpyrrolidine-3,4-diol (**25a**) :

¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 11.80 (1H, s), 8.10 (1H, s), 7.74–7.70 (1H, t, *J* 5.4 Hz, D₂O exchangeable), 7.39 (1H, s), 5.22–5.09 (3H, bs), 4.36–4.33 (1H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz), 4.22–4.18 (1H, dd, *J* 4.5 and 4.8 Hz), 3.94–3.91 (1H, t, *J* 4.2 Hz), 3.53–3.42 (4H, m), 3.23–3.19 (1H, dd, *J* 4.8 and 4.2 Hz), 0.89–0.80 (1H, m), 0.24–0.18 (2H, m), 0.05–0.01 (2H, m); MS (ES⁺) 320.3 (M+1), (ES⁻) 318.3 (M-1), HPLC purity : 98.67%.

(2*S*, 3*S*, 4*R*, 5*R*)-2-(4-(cyclohexylamino)-5*H*-pyrrolo[3, 2-*d*]pyrimidin-7-pyrimidin-7-yl)-5-hydroxymethylpyrrolidine-3,4-diol (**25b**) :

¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 11.88 (1H, s), 9.86 (1H, s), 8.79 (1H, s), 8.09–8.05 (1H, d, *J* 4.8 Hz, D₂O exchangeable), 5.64–5.25 (3H, bs, D₂O exchangeable), 4.80–4.77 (1H, d, *J* 5.4 Hz), 4.71–4.69 (1H, m), 4.43–4.38 (1H, dd, *J* 4.6 and 4.2 Hz), 4.15–4.12 (1H, dd, *J* 5.2 and 4.8 Hz), 3.74–3.71 (2H, d, *J* 5.4 Hz), 3.48–3.45 (1H, m), 2.01–1.97 (4H, m), 1.69–1.65 (6H, m); MS (ES⁺) 348.3 (M+1), (ES⁻) 346.3 (M-1), HPLC purity : 99.19%.

(2*S*, 3*S*, 4*R*, 5*R*)-2-(4-(cyclopentylamino)-5*H*-pyrrolo[3, 2-*d*]pyrimidin-7-pyrimidin-7-yl)-5-hydroxymethylpyrrolidine-3,4-diol (**25c**) :

¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 12.25 (1H, s), 9.85 (1H, s), 8.66 (1H, s), 8.04–8.03 (1H, d, *J* 3 Hz, D₂O exchangeable), 5.79–4.89 (3H, bs, D₂O exchangeable), 4.80–4.77 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz), 4.61–4.59 (1H, m), 4.43–4.38 (1H, dd, *J* 4.8 and 5.1 Hz), 4.13–4.06 (1H, m), 3.74–3.72 (2H, d, *J* 5.1 Hz), 3.51–3.48 (1H, m), 2.08–1.99 (4H, m), 1.72–1.59 (4H, m); MS (ES⁺) 334.3 (M+1), (ES⁻) 332.3 (M-1), HPLC purity : 95.90%.

(2*S*, 3*S*, 4*R*, 5*R*)-2-(4-(piperidino)-5*H*-pyrrolo[3, 2-*d*]pyrimidin-7-pyrimidin-7-yl)-5-hydroxymethylpyrrolidine-3,4-diol (**25d**) :

¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 11.51 (1H, s), 8.22 (1H, s), 7.54 (1H, s), 5.57–4.87 (3H, bs, D₂O exchangeable), 4.40–4.37 (1H, d, *J* 5.1 Hz), 4.22–4.18 (1H, dd, *J* 5.1 and 4.8 Hz), 4.01–3.98 (1H, m), 3.76–3.74 (2H, d, *J* 5.1 Hz), 3.60–3.55 (1H, m), 3.25–3.24

(4H, m), 1.6 (6H, m); MS (ES⁺) 334.3 (M+1), (ES⁻) 332.3 (M-1), HPLC purity : 98.50%.

(2*S*, 3*S*, 4*R*, 5*R*)-2-(4-(pyrrolidino)-5*H*-pyrrolo[3, 2-*d*]pyrimidin-7-pyrimidin-7-yl)-5-hydroxymethylpyrrolidine-3,4-diol (**25e**) :

¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 11.6 (1H, s), 8.92 (1H, s), 8.66 (1H, s), 5.73–4.85 (3H, bs, D₂O exchangeable), 4.84–4.81 (1H, d, *J* 9.3 Hz), 4.45–4.40 (1H, dd, *J* 4.8 and 4.8 Hz), 4.10–4.00 (1H, m), 3.76–3.74 (2H, d, *J* 4.8 Hz), 3.52–3.49 (1H, m), 3.40–3.38 (4H, m), 2.08–2.07 (4H, m); MS (ES⁺) 320.3 (M+1), (ES⁻) 318.3 (M-1), HPLC purity : 99.36%.

(2*S*, 3*S*, 4*R*, 5*R*)-2-(4-(3-chlorobenzylamino)-5*H*-pyrrolo[3, 2-*d*]pyrimidin-7-pyrimidin-7-yl)-5-hydroxymethylpyrrolidine-3,4-diol (**25f**) :

¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 11.62 (1H, s), 8.33–8.29 (1H, t, *J* 6 Hz, D₂O exchangeable), 8.17 (1H, s), 7.53 (1H, s), 7.41 (1H, s), 7.38–7.28 (3H, m), 5.54–5.38 (3H, bs, D₂O exchangeable), 4.75–4.73 (1H, d, *J* 6 Hz), 4.35–4.32 (1H, dd, *J* 3.6 and 3.8 Hz), 4.24–4.20 (1H, dd, *J* 5.1 and 4.8 Hz), 4.00–3.97 (1H, m), 3.60–3.59 (2H, d, *J* 2.1 Hz), 3.25–3.22 (2H, m); MS (ES⁺) 390.3 (M+1), (ES⁻) 388.0 (M-1), HPLC purity : 98.40%.

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